

China and Nigeria Cooperation on Tertiary Education Development

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Abstract: Purpose: This paper assessed the contribution of China to the development of Nigerian tertiary education.

Method: Secondary data that were used in the paper. The secondary data were collected from government documents, print resources and online publications. Content analysis was used to narrow the literature to the theme of the study.

Findings: The paper revealed that funding aids, infrastructure facilities development, provision of academic training opportunities, research development and establishment of a centre for the studies of China-Nigeria relation and culture are some of the contributions of China to the development of tertiary education in Nigeria.

Recommendations: The government should strengthen the bilateral relations it has with the government of China to aid development in tertiary education.

Keywords: China, Nigeria, Tertiary education.

Introduction

China's aid and other engagements in Africa have been relatively on the rise since the turn of the millennium, following the establishment of a forum for China–Africa cooperation. China has always emphasized that it has a different ideology than most Western countries regarding its foreign policy through the win-win cooperation with other countries and avoidance of any traits of 'interference' towards another nation. In other words, China's investment in Africa has never had a political condition this is because China's preference for dialogue and partnership over confrontation and alliance has created greater resonance, unlike the West's way of investment, which for decades has deprived Africa of real economic independence (Omoruyi et al, 2017; Chidiebere, & Hui, 2018).

China has also promoted the idea of a mutually beneficial partnership with Africa, in which both parties gain from the relationship through the resource for infrastructure development

agreement. The —win-winll cooperation between China and Africa – has been under criticism by Western media, academia, and governments. However, it does appeal to African leaders and many Africans. Apart from economic engagements between Africa, education has become a great component of the Sino-African framework. Education Exchanges between Africa and China date back to the pre-independence era, which is divided into three phases: the initial phase was marked by the establishment of diplomatic ties between China and some African countries such as Kenya, Egypt, Uganda and Cameroon, in 1956. This saw 24 exchange students travel to China. The second stage involved the period of reforms from 1970 to 1980. This also recorded an increase in the number of African students travelling to China for studies. The official document of the Chinese government recorded that 4,570 Africans had studied in China by the end of 1996. More so, within this period china has also made an impact on the continent through the donations of educational equipment and laboratories (Omoruyi et al, 2017). The final phase started with the Millennium Declaration of FORUM FOR CHINA – AFRICA COOPERATION FOCAC (2000). FOCAC is a triennial process at the Heads of State level, bolstered by systematic visits to African countries by the top Chinese leadership (Omoruyi et al, 2017; Chidiebere, & Hui 2018).

To ensure sustainable development in Africa, educational issues are to be given more attention under the FOCAC framework. The FOCAC educational agenda has developed from academic exchanges, government scholarships, higher education cooperation and research projects, dispatch of teachers, and human resources development to cover technical and vocational education and training, distance learning (remote learning), school construction, dispatch of volunteers, teaching Chinese as a foreign language, and mutual recognition of academic qualification. In its aim to promote access and quality education, China is trying not to leave any African countries behind therefore the dragon economy takes the continent as a whole in terms of bolstering the continent's educational system (Omoruyi et al, 2017; Chidiebere, & Hui 2018). The Republic Peoples' of China since the 1960's has been undertaking different programmes in Nigeria. It is very important to examine the contribution of China to the development of tertiary education in Nigeria.

Concept of Tertiary Education

Tertiary education is an educational system designed to solve local, national and international pressing problems (Ogunode & Musa, 2024). Tertiary education fosters individual development and growth as well as impacts positively on society at large (Schrader-King, 2024). Tertiary education is a subset of the general society comprising the collection of different people with different cultural and ethnic backgrounds, lifestyles, living standards and moral values (Ogunode & Odo, 2023) participating in educational activities. Tertiary education can be defined as the planned and organized system of learning designed for the total development of individuals and the total transformation of society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie 2023).

Tertiary education is an educational system that advances the implementation of the teaching programme, research programme and community service programme for the socio-economic, socio-cultural and technological development of a particular country (Ogunode & Mcbrown, 2022; Ogunode & Ayeni, 2023). Tertiary education or higher education covers a wider range of higher institutions of learning which include universities and other institutions such as polytechnics, mono-technics, colleges of education, and technical training institutes, (Idowu 2020). Ibrahim (2017) stated that higher institutions are very important tools in meeting the socio-cultural and developmental needs of a country. The above is validated by scholars who argue that the **founding of tertiary institutions brings about social and economic development to the host community (Ayeni, & Ezirim, 2023).**

However, not having the required education can result in a lack of access to participating

in the democratic process of one's state or society. Thus, it has been noted that a low level of access to education has resulted in the absence of popular participation and involvement in the decision-making of government (Ayeni, 2017b). The fact is that the role of education, especially tertiary education is germane to the overall development of every society. The Nigerian tertiary institutions are plagued with the following challenges; poor funding, inadequate infrastructure facilities, shortage of academic staff, poor research funding, insecurity, unstable academic programmes, strike actions, ineffective capacity development programmes, brain-drain, unconducive learning environment and poor motivation of staff. The tertiary institutions need support from international institutions, private institutions and aid from international communities (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Ogwuche, 2023).

Contribution of China to the Development of Tertiary Education in Nigeria

There are many contributions of China to the development of tertiary education in Nigeria. Some of these contributions include; the provision of financial aid, infrastructure facilities development, provision of academic training opportunities, research development and establishment of a centre for the studies of China-Nigeria relations and culture.

Provision of financial aids

Funding is very critical for the development of tertiary education, and money is the lifeblood of every organisation or society (Ayeni, 2017). Adequate funding helps in the realization of tertiary education objectives and goals. Funding is a major problem tertiary institutions in Nigeria are facing. The Republic of China since entering into a bilateral agreement with the Nigerian government has been providing some financial aid to support the development of education, especially tertiary institutions. Many Nigerian educational institutions have benefited from the financial aid of the government of China. Premium-times (2020) quoted that the former Minister of State for Budget and National Planning noted that Nigeria received \$26.94 billion in Development Assistance funds from International Donors between 2015 and 2020. Mr Agba made this known while briefing the House of Representatives Committee on Civil Society and Development Partners on Donor Funds Receipts, Transfers and Disbursement to Government Agencies, Civil Society and Non-Governmental Organisations in Nigeria. Breaking down the figure, Mr Agba observed that the amount comprised \$ 2.34 billion received in 2015, \$1.15 billion received in 2016 and \$ 774.93 million collected in 2017. The minister said that \$22.02 billion was obtained in 2018, while \$655.64 million was received in 2019 and \$5.64 million got in 2020. According to him, these donations come from the European Development Fund (EDF) and the United Nations Development Systems (UNDS). He explained that some of the funds also came from China through the Bilateral Agreement between the Government of Nigeria and the People's Republic of China signed in 1972. Mr Agba said some funds came from Japan Activities in Nigeria via the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), and Korean International Cooperation Agency (KOICA). He said that others came from the Department for International Development (DFID), the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and the German International Cooperation (GIZ). According to him, the ministry does not receive donor funds and, hence cannot transfer or disburse what is not received. He said that Nigeria does not currently qualify for budget support because it is not classified as very poor but as a lower middle-income country that is only qualified for project/programme support. "The implication of this is that Donors do not give us the funds for management, rather Donors work with the sectoral stakeholders to fund the project directly after identifying the needs of the MDAs/States in line with the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness. "For clarification, the Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning is responsible for coordinating Nigeria's multilateral and bilateral economic cooperation including development aid and technical assistance programmers by signing cooperation agreements. Ogunode, Ukozor, and Agbo, (2024) observed that China and

other international institutions have contributed to the development of education via their financial aid.

Infrastructure facilities development

It is believed that democracy is expected to deliver the greatest good like infrastructural facilities to the greatest number of people. This is corroborated by scholars who argue that democracy itself is capable of bringing about political development where there is happiness for the greatest number of citizens (Ayeni & Sani, 2021). This development is because infrastructural development enhances human security (Ayeni, Andeshi, & Uzoigwe, 2022). This is even as Ayeni, Abdullahi and Andeshi (2021) agreed that massive infrastructural development provides a suitable environment and support for the development of entrepreneurship skills and industrialisation. Based on the vital role that infrastructure plays in the development of every nation, the People's Republic of China has contributed to the infrastructure development of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Infrastructure facility is viewed by Ogunode (2020) as those facilities aiding the delivery of academic and non-academic services in educational institutions. Infrastructural facilities include; libraries, laboratories, halls, offices, administrative blocks, hostels, road facilities, water, electricity, internet et cetera. The availability of infrastructural facilities in adequate quantities will support the effective administration of educational institutions and the inadequacies will prevent the effective administration of educational institutions. This is even as Ayeni, Sani, Andeshi, Ibrahim and Adamu (2020) noted that infrastructural development has intended and unintended benefits for the youth. China's government has assisted many tertiary institutions in developing their facilities such as laboratories, libraries, lecture halls and provision of solar lights. Recently, the China embassy in Nigeria donated a Free Trade Zone Online Chinese Classroom facilities to the Ogun State Ministry of Education. Ojuroungbe, (2024) reported that the Chinese Consul-General, Lagos, Yan Yuqing, has reaffirmed China's commitment to supporting the development of Nigeria's education system. The Chinese Consul-General said the embassy remains "steadfast in its support for education in Nigeria, as it is an important pillar for the country's future development." The Chinese Consul-General, Lagos, Yan Yuqing noted this on Wednesday during the launching of the free Chinese Online Classroom Project donated by the Ogun-Guangdong Free Trade Zone in the Igbesa area of Ogun State. Yuqing, while revealing that the project was in collaboration with the Chinese Ministry of Education, said the Free Trade Zone Online Chinese Classroom was a significant milestone in the cultural and economic collaboration between Nigeria and China. She added, "The online class aims to foster cultural exchange and strengthen Nigeria-China relations by offering Mandarin Chinese learning opportunities to tertiary students and interested individuals. With a focus on technology transfer, career enhancement, and global preparedness, the project signifies OGFTZ's commitment to facilitating a positive environment for Nigerian and Chinese businesses". On his part, the Deputy General Manager of China-Africa Investment FZC, Kevin Liu, explained that the programme's key component is to equip the university undergraduates and widen their chances in skill acquisition and economic empowerment. He added that apart from the involvement of the academy environment, the locals who are interested in learning the Chinese language will also benefit from the programme. Also, the Chinese Consulate donated a borehole facility to the University of Lagos to support infrastructure facilities at the university. China as a state is providing access to infrastructural facilities in Nigeria because of its bilateral relationship with the country. This is because the government must provide those amenities that empower (Ayeni, Sani, Idris, & Uzoigwe, 2019). Misuse of money meant for infrastructure has put members of the public in a state of poor human security (Ayeni, Andeshi, & Uzoigwe, 2022; Ayeni, Doosuur, & Kefas, 2021)). The above development informs countries like China to show concern. Oyeleke (2017) reported that in a bid to tackle the challenges posed by the inadequate supply of potable water at the University of Lagos, the

Chinese Consulate in Lagos has donated a modern borehole to the university. The Consul General of China in Lagos, His Excellency, Mr. Chao Xiaoliang, said the project was executed under the framework of 'China-Africa People-to-People Friendship Action.' He said the project, which is located within the Faculty of Education, was meant to enhance the water supply on campus. This, he said, would make the university environment more conducive to teaching and learning. Xiaoliang explained that the 'China-Africa People-to-People Friendship Action' was aimed at fostering better relations between Chinese companies and their host countries. He noted that the donation was in furtherance of the consulate's corporate social responsibility initiative in Nigeria. He said, "CGC began operation in Nigeria 34 years ago, that is 1983. Ever since then, we have rapidly grown into business, including consultancy, investment, infrastructure, logistics and trading with its footprint across.

Provision of academic training opportunities

The China-Nigeria bilateral agreement also covers areas of academic training. Foreign training is according to Ogunode, and Abayomi (2023) an organized training programme received in another country for career development. Foreign training is a form of training that exposes the receiver to a new form of exposure, education and experience nationally and internationally. Foreign training is a form of international training received by a trainee to expose the trainee to a new level of education. Foreign training is one of the effective and tested means for career enlargement, enrichment and performance. The objective of foreign training is to expose the trainee to new forms of skills and knowledge that most international training programs are specifically designed to leverage on the trainee's professional network and focus on creating the perfect learning and sharing environment to broaden the trainee perspective and grasp new approaches practised by foreign professionals (Ogunode, et al 2023). Chidiebere, (2018) asserted that in terms of scholarship allocation, each year, the Chinese government awards 40 scholarships to Nigerian students to study in China. This scholarship includes undergraduate, master and doctorate studies. These scholarships cover areas such as mining, industrial fishery, medicine, accountancy, commerce and distribution, renewable energy, environmental sciences, network and telecommunications, management of agricultural co-operatives, computer science, communication and information, electricity, international relations, international business law, and Chinese language. Currently, about 237 Nigerian students are said to be studying in China under government scholarship. This is also in line with President Xi Jinping's pledges to enhance development experiences by offering occupational training courses for African youths and training young talent in agricultural science, increasing the Chinese government scholarships from 30, 000 in 2015 to 50,000 in 2018 for Africa and inviting 2,000 young people from Africa to visit China. Also, Omoruyi, Yao, Abah & Mvuh (2017) maintained that to promote Africa's independent educational development by strengthening its capacity to create its own cultural and human resources, China is offering scholarships to Africa in many areas: sciences, engineering or technology fields, reflecting the demands from the African countries to build up necessary skills. International institutions and China have assisted Nigerian educational institutions teachers in acquiring skills and new methodologies through their various capacity-building programmes (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Ogwuche 2023; Adekunle, 2022; Channy, & Ogunniran, 2019)

Research development

The embassy of China in Abuja has assisted in the development of research programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Ogunode and Ade (2023) defined research as the process of finding solutions to existing problems facing the nation. Research is a systematic activity leading to problem-solving in societies. Udechukwu, C. (2016) reported that the Chinese Cultural Research Centre of Nigeria was commissioned at the Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, by the cultural attache of the Chinese Embassy in Abuja, Yan Xiang Dong. The research centre is the first in Nigeria. The vice chancellor of the school, Prof. J. E. Ahaneku, said the

university was delighted to host the centre. Chinese Cultural Research Centre is meant to promote research in the university and aid research development. China and other international organizations in Nigeria have positively contributed to the development of research in Nigerian tertiary institutions (Mohammed, & Ogunode, 2024).

Establishment of the Centre for the studies of China-Nigeria relation and culture, languages

Republic of People's China has supported tertiary institutions in Nigeria in the establishment of different centres and institutes. The embassy of China in Abuja has facilitated the establishment of different centres in the Nigerian tertiary institutions especially the universities (Femi, 2018). For instance, Chidiebere, (2018) observed that even though China and Nigeria have vastly different historical experiences and cultural traditions, China has been remarkably successful in its efforts to promote China-Nigeria education cooperation. In 2008, Nnamdi Azikiwe University in Akwa, Nigeria, established a Confucius Institute to teach the Chinese language to Nigerian students. As business linkages between China and Nigeria have grown speedily in recent years, the institute was a successful project. Its success was acknowledged on June 29, when the Chinese embassy in Abuja announced the establishment of Nigeria's first Chinese Cultural Research Center. The embassy also pledged to create an Igbo language institute in China to encourage Chinese university graduates to work for Chinese companies in Nigeria. In 2009, the University of Lagos established another Confucius Institute. Following the demand and the deepening cooperation between Nigeria and China, the Chinese embassy in 2016 opened a Chinese learning Centre in Abuja as a sister institute of Nnamdi Azikiwe University with affiliation to Xiamen University in China.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined the contributions of China to the development of Nigerian tertiary education. The paper concluded that the contributions of China to the development of Nigerian tertiary education include; the provision of financial aid, infrastructure facilities development, provision of academic training opportunities, research development and establishment of a centre for the studies of China-Nigeria relations and culture.

Based on the findings, the paper recommends that the Government should strengthen bilateral relations with the government of China to aid development in tertiary education. Olalekan A. B. (2024) recommended that China should support Africa's aspiration to become a member of the UN Security Council, to promote solidarity and for a better future for humanity. Both should strengthen their cooperation and understanding to promote shared interests, shared rights and shared responsibilities in global affairs. As the current lopsided international order has done a disservice to the continent, the open, inclusive, clean and beautiful world that will foster lasting peace, common security and common prosperity is what Africa needs as the world is poised for a new order.

Secondly, both the federal and state governments should increase education allocation to a quantum sum that will revolutionise the educational sector and tertiary institutions in particular.

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